

DESIGN AND MANUFACTURE OF SOLAR POWERED COMPOSITE RACE CAR

M. Gokool and C. J. von Klemperer

Centre of Composite and Smart Materials, School of Mechanical Engineering, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, 4041, South Africa.

SUMMARY: The design and manufacture processes of epoxy based composite components for a solar powered race vehicle are considered in this paper. The following components of the solar car were manufactured from composite materials: upper and lower shells, front rims, driver's seat, wheel spat and canopy. The moulds for all these components were also designed and manufactured at the School of Mechanical Engineering, University of KwaZulu-Natal. The components and moulds were modelled using CAD software Solid Edge. The finite element analysis software package MSC Nastran was used in the strength analysis of the components with the conditions expected during racing providing the loading. The composite materials used for the manufacture of the various components for the solar car allows for a reduction in the mass of the car and therefore an improvement in overall performance and efficiency.

KEYWORDS: carbon fibre wheels, sandwich composite, mould design, solar power, World Solar Challenge.

INTRODUCTION

The design and manufacture of a solar powered race car began in 1999 as a final year project for mechanical engineering students at the University of Kwa-Zulu Natal (UKZN) with the aim of competing in the World Solar Challenge (WSC) in Australia. The WSC is the most prestigious international solar event; it promotes and celebrates education and technical excellence, drawing attention to the imperatives of sustainable transport [1]. The challenge attracts teams from universities and large corporations from around the world. The competition allows entrants to showcase the latest technologies and developments in solar power and the use of composite materials in vehicle design.

The WSC is a biennial event held in Australia that aims to further research and development in renewable solar technology. The event takes the form of a race, which runs for 3010km, from Darwin to Adelaide along the Stuart Highway. Entrants in this event are required to conform to all regulations outlined by the WSC, in essence implies that the vehicle has to be powered only by solar energy for the duration of the race. The event lasts for about 10 days with racing only taking place between 8am and 5pm on allocated days. The challenges facing any team entering the event is the extent to which many aspects of the vehicle design have to be compromised. These include the vehicle aerodynamics, solar array efficiency and weight, along with the reliability and overall speed. A good balance of these factors will determine the success of the car in completing the race.

Most of the international solar teams use composite materials in the manufacture of the outer shells of their vehicles due to the superior mechanical properties of the materials. The UKZN solar car makes more extensive use of composite materials with various other components being manufactured from these materials. Carbon fibre/epoxy composite is used to manufacture the shells and front rims while a sandwich composite of carbon fibre and Herex core foam with epoxy resin is used for the seat. The wheel spat and canopy were also manufactured as sandwich composites with glass fibre and medium density Herex core foam again with epoxy resin.

The components and their moulds were all manufactured at the School of Mechanical Engineering, UKZN. All moulds were made from Supawood sheeting (an affordable and dimensionally stable processed wood) which was profile cut and used in a wine-box construction. An exception is the rim moulds which were turned from solid Supawood. Thin aluminium sheeting of 0.5mm thickness was then fastened over the profiled wood frames to give a smooth and even surface on which the components could be moulded.

CARBON FIBRE FRONT WHEELS

The solar car has two front wheels and a single drive wheel at the rear. The rear wheel is a special design which includes a hub motor [2]. The UKZN solar car will be one of the few race vehicles that utilises their own wheels, most teams purchase expensive wheels for their cars. The front wheels are unique to the university and is made entirely from carbon fibre and epoxy resin with the exception of the aluminium hub as shown in figure 1. The entire wheel was made up of five separate components that are bonded together to form the completed wheel. These components are the aluminium hub, two composite wheel disks and two composite rim sections. The disk design has many advantages over the previous spoked wheel design. Drag forces are reduced because air cannot flow through the wheel as it did with a spoked wheel. The disk wheels are strong enough to support the weight of the car and the driver under the dynamic loads expected in the race and lightweight to improve performance.

Fig. 1: Exploded view of the rim

Analysis

The wheel was analysed using the finite element analysis software MSC Nastran for different loading conditions; including static weight, braking fatigue, turning and wheel lock using the properties shown in table 1. Wheel lock occurs when the car is moving and the wheels are not rotating but sliding. The FEA software enabled the entire front wheel assembly to be analysed. The hub, disks and rim sections were individually modelled and then analysed as a complete unit. This method of analysis made it possible to determine the effect of a given

loading condition on the assembly as a whole or on each component separately. The effects of the various loads were negligible on the hub and rim sections hence the analysis of the disks is of primary importance.

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of Carbon/Epoxy Composite Sheet used in Construction of the Front Wheels [3]

Properties for Carbon/Epoxy Composite Sheet		
Property	Unit	Value
Coefficient of thermal expansion – Longitudinal	x10-6 K-1	2.1
Coefficient of thermal expansion – Transverse	x10-6 K-1	2.1
Compressive Strength – Longitudinal	MPa	570
Compressive Strength – Transverse	MPa	570
Density	g cm-3	1.6
Shear modulus – in-plane	GPa	5
Shear strength – in-plane	MPa	90
Tensile strength – Longitudinal	MPa	600
Tensile strength – Transverse	MPa	600
Ultimate Compressive Strain – Longitudinal	%	0.8
Ultimate Compressive Strain – Transverse	%	0.8
Ultimate Shear Strain – in-plane	%	1.8
Ultimate Tensile Strain – Longitudinal	%	0.85
Ultimate Tensile Strain – Transverse	%	0.85
Volume fraction of fibres	%	50
Young's Modulus – Longitudinal	GPa	70
Young's Modulus – Transverse	GPa	70

Table 2 shows the results of the analysis of the carbon fibre wheels for the various loading conditions [4]. The results show that the maximum displacements are small (less than a millimeter) and the maximum stresses are acceptable when compared to the mechanical properties in table 1. The turning loading condition shows the smallest force but the highest stress, this is so because the turning force acts on the circumference of the wheel but in the axial direction creating a smaller moment of inertia and therefore higher stress. The static loading condition (shown in figure 2) acts in the radial direction while the braking and wheel lock forces act tangentially to the wheel therefore the resulting in higher moments of inertia and lower stresses. The results show that the design is capable of withstanding the harsh conditions that are expected during racing.

Table 2: Results of FEA of front wheel

	Force (N)	Maximum Displacement (mm)	Maximum Stress (MPa)
Static loading	3500	0.0261	6.28
Braking	2900	0.2	52.89
Turning	1750	negligible	59.41
Wheel lock	2900	0.2	52.89

Fig. 2: FEA for the static loading condition

Manufacturing Process

Moulds

The disks and rim sections of the front wheels are manufactured on a three part mould as shown in figure 3. The three parts are also clamped together for secondary bonding of the wheel. The moulds were turned from Supawood and then sealed, painted and polished to give a high gloss surface finish.

Fig. 3: Three part mould for front wheels

Lay-up

The disks were manufactured on parts 1 and 3 of the mould. The disks were made in a wet lay-up process and vacuum bagged. The lay-up consisted of eight layers of 200g/m² plain weave carbon fibre orientated at $[0/45^{\circ}]_8$. The rim section of the front wheel was made on part 2 of the mould from eight layers of 200g/m² plain weave carbon fibre. The two right angle bends in close proximity to one another caused difficulty in the lay-up and hence a lot of experimental work was done with the lay-up procedure using cheaper glass fibre with epoxy. Figure 4 below shows the first and final experimental lay-ups. The lay-up on the left broke at the lip recess due to inadequate compaction. The final experimental lay-up on the right was reinforced with four layers of unidirectional glass roving on the lip. The final glass fibre lay-up showed good compaction, strength and rigidity; hence the carbon fibre lay-up followed this method.

Fig. 4: Experimental lay-ups of the rim section

Assembly and Testing

The wheel was assembled together using a two part epoxy adhesive. The assembly of the wheel was done in two stages; firstly, adhesive was applied to the disks and rim sections and they were clamped together in the mould to form two wheel halves. Secondly, the wheel halves were bonded together over the hub as shown in figure 5 thus bonding the 2 rim sections together. The hub and wheel halves were held concentrically in a lathe during bonding.

Fig. 5: Assembly of the wheel

The completed wheel was mounted to a bracket and fitted onto the rear suspension. Steel plate of mass of approximately 350 kg (equal to the entire mass of the car) was placed on the rear suspension. The wheel was not damaged during this test and a further test was conducted to simulate cornering at high speeds. The wheel failed in this test under a load of 750N due to a secondary bond cracking. Subsequent wheels were bonded with greater care with a stronger epoxy adhesive and showed better results.

THE SHELLS

There were many factors that needed to be considered when determining the shape of the solar car. The most critical of these factors in terms of performance of the solar car is the reduction of aerodynamic drag forces and skin friction. Other factors include the spatial constraints of the driver and controls and the WSC rules that limit the dimensions of the race vehicles. The WSC also sets a maximum allowable surface area of 8m^2 for solar panels [1]. Therefore the car has to be large enough to accommodate driver and the full quota of solar panels but small enough to adhere to the rules. The design of the car was based on an aerofoil shape that followed the Kutta-Joukowski profile [5] as shown in figure 6. The Kutta-Joukowski profile

and high gloss surface finish obtained after painting and polishing resulted in a frontal area of $A_F = 1,1\text{m}^2$ and a coefficient of drag, $C_D < 0,16$.

Fig. 6: Model of shell showing aerofoil shape with the Kutta-Joukowski profile

Manufacture of the Mould

Both the upper and lower shells of the solar car were manufactured on the same male mould. Using a single mould to manufacture both the shells ensured that the shells fit together properly and also greatly reduced the overall production cost. To produce the framework for the plug, a wine-box structure was modelled using CAD software Solid Edge. Laser profiled Supawood was assembled into an interlocking framework for the plug. Polystyrene was hot wire cut to the required shape and used as the core material to fill the spaces in between the framework. The nose cone, which is a body of revolution, was constructed separately from the rest of the plug using the hollow template method of manufacture. The nose cone was then bonded to the rest of the plug. Expandable foam was used to fill the gaps between the polystyrene and framework and to create an easily sandable surface. The surface was sealed, painted and polished to produce an exceptionally smooth finish.

Manufacture of the Shells

Both shells were prepared by wet lay-up from 4 layers of 2x2 twill weave carbon fibre and Epolam 2020 epoxy resin. For the first shell, the fibres were orientated at $(0^\circ/90^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ)$ but this was changed to $(45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ)$ for the second shell to enable the layers to be more easily positioned. Once cured the shells were covered with black plastic bags and post-cured in sunlight where the measured temperatures reached 60°C . The shells were flipped over regularly to ensure optimal and even post-curing.

Both shells lacked stiffness and was bending under their own weight. This problem was anticipated and reinforcing polystyrene ribs were strategically placed effectively creating top hat stiffeners as shown in figure 7. The position of the reinforcing ribs was determined using FEA software MSC Nastran. The polystyrene ribs were used instead of the more conventional method of using core foam to form a sandwich composite because the shells have a large surface area of nearly 20 m^2 and using core foam would be both expensive and heavy. Expanded polystyrene foam and glass fibre was used as a sandwich composite in specific areas on the upper shell so that cut outs could be made to accommodate the canopy, as shown in figure 7. Similar cut outs were made on the lower shell for the three wheels.

Fig. 7: Upper shell showing reinforcing ribs and cut-out for driver

SANDWICH COMPOSITE COMPONENTS

The seat, wheel spat and canopy of the solar car were manufactured as sandwich composite constructions. Sandwich composites were chosen for these components because of a need for high bending strength of the panels. A cored laminate under bending load can be likened to an I-beam structure where the skins act as the flanges, taking the tensile and compressive loads and the core acts as the web, taking the shear load. The core must also have sufficient compressive strength to prevent the relatively thin skins from wrinkling and failing by buckling.

Fig. 8: Laminate in bending [6]

Profiles of Composite Components

Each of the three sandwich structure components follows a profile that is best suited to fulfill its purpose. The shape of the seat is constrained in part by the size and shape of the solar car shells. For the best possible aerodynamic configuration to be achieved, most if not all of the driver's body must be accommodated within the body shells. The seat design is basically a flat panel that is moulded to comfortably support the contour of the driver's body in a reclining position as shown in figure 9. The horizontal driving position ensures that very little of the driver's head is protruding above the shells and hence the canopy which encapsulates the driver can be as small as possible. Even a small canopy results in an increase in the frontal area of the car and therefore an increase in drag force. To reduce the drag force, the canopy was designed according to a tapered Kutta-Joukowski profile. The top section of the canopy was flattened to increase the surface area for the use of solar panels as shown in figure 10. This also made it easier to produce the moulds and final component.

Fig. 9: Profile of the Seat

Fig. 10: CAD model of canopy

The function of the wheel spat is to reduce drag forces on the car because the swingarm and the hub motor are not streamlined. The width of the hub motor created unnecessary drag forces, therefore an aerodynamic wheel spat was designed and manufactured as shown in figure 11. The wheel spat has a modified NACA 0028-14 (National Advisory Committee for Aeronautics) profile. This profile, unlike the conventional NACA profile, does not have a camber angle and is symmetrical about the chord. This leads to a reduction in drag and the absence of any lift force coefficients.

Fig. 11: Sandwich composite wheel spat

Production of Low Cost Moulds

The financial pressure on the project created a need to develop low cost approaches to manufacture the moulds. The moulds for the three sandwich composite components were manufactured at the School of Mechanical Engineering workshop and cost less than ZAR600 (€ 75) to produce [7]. The method of producing the moulds was low cost and simple. The moulds were modelled with the CAD software Solid Edge as shown in figure 12 and full size, two dimensional profiles were printed on paper. The printed profiles were attached to Supawood and then cut using a band saw. The profiled pieces of wood were made into a stable wine-box structure using cross braces. Aluminium sheeting of 0,5mm thickness was fastened over the wine-box structure to give a smooth and even surface as shown in figure 13. Where possible, symmetry was used so that one mould could be used for both halves of the part e.g. the wheel spat. The moulds are robust and can be used to produce about 25 parts before degradation begins to occur.

Fig. 12: Solid Edge model of seat mould

Fig. 13: Completed seat and wheel spat mould

The Lay-up Process

All sandwich composites were prepared by a wet lay-up process and vacuum bagged. The seat construction consisted of two layers of carbon fibre on either side of 10mm thick, high density core foam. The carbon cloth used was 200g/m², 2x2 twill weave, carbon fibre. The core foam was Herex C70.90 cross linked PVC foam which has a density of 90 kg/m³. Herex C70.90 is thermoforming foam and had to be heated to a temperature of between 115° to 130°C to be formed to the contour of the seat. The large curves in the foam were created by slowly heating an area across the width of the sheet until it became pliable, the foam was then bent by hand until the approximate curve was taken. The foam was held in this position until it cooled sufficiently to hold its new shape. Once the foam sheet had been shaped to approximately that of the seat it was placed onto the mould. A vacuum bag was placed over the foam so that a vacuum could be drawn to hold the foam onto the mould. The canopy and wheel spat were made from 5mm thick Herex C70.55 core foam with glass fibre and epoxy resin skins. The thinner Herex C70.55 core foam was not thermoformed but obtained the required shape of the mould whilst the vacuum was drawn. The sandwich composite produced stiff, strong and lightweight components which give an advantage when racing.

CONCLUSION

The use of composite materials for the various components of the solar car meant a reduction in mass and an increase in efficiency. The carbon fibre shells are ideally suited to racing since they are lightweight and smooth. The carbon fibre wheel is of a high strength and will withstand the conditions that the car will encounter. The design of the carbon fibre wheel adds a new facet to the already unique design of the solar car. The production of the new rim was a challenge in itself and final product is an advanced composite wheel which will improve the performance of the solar car. The use of composite materials in the design and manufacture of the solar car has given an added dimension to an already competitive product. The components produced are of a high quality even though low cost methods were used in their manufacture. This method of producing low cost reusable moulds shows promise in the South African reinforced polymer industry.

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://www.wsc.org.au> , Official website of World Solar Challenge, 2005
- [2] Ramsden, V.S., Mecrow, B.C. and Lovatt, H.C., “Design of an in-wheel motor for a solar-powered electric vehicle”, EMD (1997)
- [3] <http://www.efunda.com/materials>
- [4] Gokool, M. and von Klemperer, C. J., “Design and Manufacture of Composite Solar Car”, *Composites Africa*, 2004, pp. 113-121.
- [5] Houghton, E.L. and Brock, A.E., “Aerodynamics for engineering students”, Edward Arnold (Publishers) Ltd, 1960, pp.282-288.
- [6] SP Systems Guide to Composites Brochure, <http://www.spsystems.com>
- [7] von Klemperer, C.J., Verijenko V.E. and Gokool, M., “Solar Powered Race Car: High Tech At Low Cost”, submitted and accepted for ICCE 12, 2005